

ISSN: 3060-4613

MAKTABGACHA
VA MAKTAB
TA'LIMI VAZIRLIGI

O'zbekiston
Milliy Pedagogika
Universiteti

No6(4)
2026

- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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AKTABGACHA VA AKTAB TA'LIMI

Pedagogika, psixologiya fanlariga ixtisoslashgan ilmiy jurnal

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Elektron nashr. 534 sahifa,
12-iyun, 2026-yil.

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Pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha: OAK Kengashi tavsiyasi (26.08.2024-y., №11-05-4381/01) asosida:

- Ekspert kengashi (29.10.2024-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (31.10.2024-y., №363/5)

Psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha: Toshkent davlat pedagogika universiteti murojaatiga asosan OAK tavsiyasi (24.04.2025-y., №11-05-2566/01):

- Ekspert kengashi (25.05.2025-y., №10)
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“Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi”
jurnali

26.09.2023-yildan

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti
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va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar
agentligi tomonidan **№C-5669363**
reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha
ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: **№136361**

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PEDAGOGICAL FOUNDATIONS FOR DEVELOPING COMPETENCIES IN ORGANIZING PRACTICAL CLASSES IN ZOOLOGY AMONG PRE-SERVICE BIOLOGY TEACHERS

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Abstract: This article discusses the pedagogical foundations for developing competencies in organizing practical classes in Zoology among pre-service biology teachers. In the process of teaching Zoology, practical classes play a significant role in strengthening students' theoretical knowledge, developing observation, analytical and experimental skills, and fostering research competencies. The study analyzes the pedagogical conditions, methods, and effective technologies for improving the practical training of future biology teachers based on a competency-based approach.

Key words: zoology, biology education, practical classes, competency, competency-based approach, pre-service teacher, pedagogical technology, laboratory work.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada bo'lajak biologiya o'qituvchilarida zoologiya fanidan amaliy mashg'ulotlarni tashkil etish kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirishning pedagogik asoslari yoritilgan. Zoologiyani o'qitish jarayonida amaliy mashg'ulotlar talabalarning nazariy bilimlarini mustahkamlash, kuzatish, tahliliy va eksperimental ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish hamda tadqiqotchilik kompetensiyalarini shakllantirishda muhim o'rin tutadi. Tadqiqotda kompetensiyaviy yondashuv asosida bo'lajak biologiya o'qituvchilarining amaliy tayyorgarligini takomillashtirishga xizmat qiluvchi pedagogik shart-sharoitlar, metodlar va samarali texnologiyalar tahlil qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: zoologiya, biologiya ta'limi, amaliy mashg'ulotlar, kompetensiya, kompetensiyaviy yondashuv, bo'lajak o'qituvchi, pedagogik texnologiya, laboratoriya ishi.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются педагогические основы развития компетенций по организации практических занятий по зоологии у будущих учителей биологии. В процессе преподавания зоологии практические занятия играют важную роль в укреплении теоретических знаний студентов, развитии наблюдательных, аналитических и экспериментальных навыков, а также в формировании исследовательских компетенций. В исследовании анализируются педагогические условия, методы и эффективные технологии совершенствования практической подготовки будущих учителей биологии на основе компетентностного подхода.

Ключевые слова: зоология, биологическое образование, практические занятия, компетенция, компетентностный подход, будущий учитель, педагогическая технология, лабораторная работа.

INTRODUCTION

Today, the profound reforms being implemented in the education system require special attention to the development of the professional competencies of teaching personnel. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, improving the quality of biology education, enhancing students' scientific literacy, and integrating modern pedagogical technologies into the educational process have been identified as priority tasks. The effective implementation of these tasks largely depends on the level of professional training of future biology teachers.

Within the system of biological sciences, Zoology occupies a special place. Zoology is a fundamental discipline aimed at studying the structure, taxonomy, ecology, evolution, and biodiversity of the animal kingdom. Along with acquiring in-depth theoretical knowledge in this subject, the effective organization of practical classes is of great importance. Through observing zoological objects, identifying and comparing species, preparing specimens, and conducting laboratory investigations, students are able to connect theoretical knowledge with practical activities.

Within the framework of the modern competency-based approach, future biology teachers are expected not only to possess theoretical knowledge but also to develop practical competencies such as fostering students' research skills, organizing laboratory and field activities, and effectively applying methods for working with biological objects. Therefore, the development of competencies related to organizing practical classes in Zoology has become one of the most relevant directions in contemporary teacher education.

Analysis indicates that although considerable attention is paid to practical training in the teaching of Zoology at higher education institutions, students still encounter difficulties in independently organizing practical activities, recording observational data, analyzing biological materials, and drawing scientific conclusions. This situation highlights the need to develop new pedagogical approaches aimed at enhancing the professional competencies of future biology teachers.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The issue of developing professional competencies among pre-service teachers through a competency-based approach has been extensively studied in modern pedagogy and biology education. In particular, the scientific works of N.A. Muslimov, M. Usmonboyeva, O.Q. Tolipov, and B.X. Xodjayev highlight the theoretical foundations of pedagogical competence development, the integration of innovative educational technologies into the teaching process, and effective mechanisms for organizing practical training.

Studies related to biology education emphasize the important role of practical classes in teaching Zoology. According to Azizxo'jayeva and other researchers, laboratory work, observations, and experimental activities not only strengthen students' theoretical knowledge but also contribute to the development of their research skills. Furthermore, practical classes organized on the basis of a competency-based approach promote independent thinking, problem-solving abilities, and professional preparedness among future teachers.

International research also confirms the significance of practical activities in biology education. E.F. Zeer emphasizes that the primary objective of the competency-based approach is to prepare specialists capable of applying theoretical knowledge in real-life professional situations. Moreover, studies conducted within the framework of STEM and STEAM education demonstrate the effectiveness of integrative and practice-oriented teaching methods in biological sciences.

The analysis of the existing literature indicates that organizing practical classes in Zoology through a competency-based approach is an important factor in developing the professional competencies of future biology teachers. However, the pedagogical conditions and mechanisms specifically related to the formation of competencies for organizing practical Zoology classes have not been sufficiently explored. Therefore, the present study aims to contribute to this area by examining the pedagogical foundations of competency development in organizing practical Zoology instruction.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study was conducted based on competency-based, systemic, activity-oriented, and learner-centered approaches.

During the research process, pedagogical, psychological, and biological literature was analyzed, and state educational standards and curricula related to biology education were examined. In addition, local and international experiences in organizing practical classes in Zoology were comparatively analyzed.

Observation, interviews, questionnaires, expert evaluation, pedagogical experiments, and diagnostic methods were employed as empirical research methods. Special diagnostic criteria were developed to assess students' competencies in organizing practical classes in Zoology.

The competencies were evaluated according to the following criteria:

- motivational criterion;
- cognitive criterion;
- practical-activity criterion;
- reflective criterion.

The motivational criterion characterized students' interest in professional activities and their attitudes toward biological research. The cognitive criterion was used to determine the level of mastery of zoological knowledge. The practical-activity criterion made it possible to assess practical skills related to organizing laboratory and field activities. The reflective criterion was aimed at identifying students' ability to analyze and evaluate their own performance.

The data obtained during the study were processed using mathematical and statistical methods, ensuring the reliability and validity of the research findings.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Cognitive Component

This component characterizes the level of mastery of zoological concepts, principles, and theories. Students should possess sufficient knowledge about the taxonomic classification of animals, their morphological and anatomical structures, ecological characteristics, and the principles of evolutionary development.

Practical-Activity Component

This component is considered the most important in organizing practical classes. Students should be able to work with microscopes, prepare biological specimens, use laboratory equipment, identify zoological objects, record observations, and analyze the obtained results.

Reflective Component

Reflective activity enables students to evaluate their knowledge and skills, identify shortcomings, and determine strategies for their professional development. The results of the study demonstrated that the development of reflective skills significantly enhances students' practical competencies.

The conducted analysis revealed that project-based learning, problem-based learning, research activities, cluster technology, the STEAM approach, and digital educational tools are highly effective in organizing practical classes in Zoology. In particular, the use of virtual laboratories and digital microscopes was found to enhance student engagement, facilitate the integration of theoretical knowledge with practical application, and promote the development of independent learning skills.

During the study, the level of development of competencies related to organizing practical classes in Zoology among pre-service biology teachers was assessed. The findings revealed that although most students possessed an adequate level of zoological knowledge, certain shortcomings remained in applying this knowledge in practical settings, independently organizing laboratory activities, and analyzing research outcomes.

Throughout the pedagogical experiment, practical classes were organized based on a competency-based approach. The integration of problem-based tasks, project activities, research methods, and interactive technologies resulted in significant positive changes in students' professional preparedness and practical performance.

At the end of the experiment, the following improvements in students' practical competencies in Zoology were identified:

- enhanced skills in identifying and classifying zoological specimens;
- improved ability to operate microscopes and other laboratory equipment;
- better competence in conducting biological observations and experiments;
- increased interest in independent research activities;
- development of skills for planning and organizing practical classes;
- strengthened abilities in recording, processing, and interpreting scientific data;
- improved reflective skills and self-assessment of professional performance.

In addition, students demonstrated greater engagement during laboratory sessions, higher motivation toward biological research, and increased confidence in conducting practical and field-based activities. These results indicate that the systematic application of innovative teaching technologies contributes significantly to the development of professional competencies among future biology teachers.

The study also identified several key factors influencing the effectiveness of competency development in Zoology practical training:

- systematic organization of practical activities;
- integration of innovative educational technologies;
- encouragement of independent research work;
- creation of a reflective learning environment;
- effective integration of theoretical and practical learning experiences.

The findings confirm that innovative approaches to organizing practical classes not only improve students' academic achievement but also foster the professional skills required for effective biology teaching in contemporary educational settings.

The following improvements in students' practical competencies in Zoology were identified:

- enhanced skills in identifying and classifying zoological specimens;
- improved proficiency in using microscopes and laboratory equipment;
- increased ability to organize biological observations and experimental activities;
- strengthened interest in independent research work;
- development of competencies in designing and planning practical classes;
- improved skills in self-assessment and reflective practice.

Furthermore, a significant increase was observed in students' participation during practical sessions, their willingness to work independently, and their professional motivation. These findings confirm that organizing practical classes through modern pedagogical technologies is an important factor in developing the professional competencies of future biology teachers.

Based on the research findings, the following factors were identified as the main contributors to the development of competencies in organizing practical Zoology classes:

- systematic organization of practical activities;
- effective use of innovative pedagogical technologies;
- encouragement of students' independent research activities;
- creation of a reflective learning environment;
- integration of theoretical knowledge with practical experience.

The results indicate that the successful implementation of these factors contributes to the formation of sustainable professional competencies, enhances students' readiness for future teaching activities, and improves the overall quality of biology teacher education.

The findings obtained in this study are consistent with a number of previous studies conducted in the field of biology education. Contemporary pedagogical concepts emphasize that the competency-based approach is aimed at developing students' ability to apply theoretical knowledge in practical situations. The results of the present study further confirm the effectiveness of this approach in enhancing professional competencies among future biology teachers.

The analysis demonstrated that the use of traditional reproductive teaching methods in organizing practical classes in Zoology does not fully support the development of students' practical competencies. In contrast, problem-based learning, project-based learning, research-oriented activities, and collaborative learning technologies significantly enhance students' professional engagement, independence, and active participation in the learning process.

An analysis of international educational practices also indicates the growing importance of practice-oriented teaching technologies in biology education. In particular, educational activities organized within the framework of STEM and STEAM approaches contribute to the development of scientific thinking, analytical reasoning, creativity, and problem-solving skills among students.

Furthermore, these approaches encourage interdisciplinary learning by integrating biological knowledge with technology, engineering, mathematics, and environmental sciences. As a result, students acquire a more comprehensive understanding of biological phenomena and develop the competencies required for effective professional practice in modern educational settings.

The findings also suggest that the integration of innovative pedagogical technologies into Zoology practical classes creates favorable conditions for strengthening students' research abilities, improving laboratory performance, and fostering lifelong learning skills. Therefore, the implementation of such approaches can be considered an effective strategy for improving the quality of biology teacher education.

Another important finding of the study was that the regular implementation of reflective activities expands students' opportunities to evaluate their own knowledge and skills, identify weaknesses, and plan their future professional development. Therefore, reflection should be regarded as an essential pedagogical condition for the development of practical competencies. Through reflective practice, students become more aware of their learning processes, develop critical self-assessment skills, and gain the ability to continuously improve their professional performance.

In addition, the study revealed that the use of digital technologies and virtual laboratories in practical Zoology classes contributes significantly to improving educational effectiveness. These tools provide students

with greater access to interactive learning resources, enable the visualization of complex biological processes, and facilitate the acquisition of practical skills in a technologically enhanced learning environment. Consequently, the integration of digital technologies into biology education offers new opportunities for advancing the professional training of future teachers and preparing them for teaching in the context of educational digitalization.

CONCLUSION

The results of the study indicate that the development of competencies related to organizing practical classes in Zoology among pre-service biology teachers is one of the key priorities of modern pedagogical education.

The competency for organizing practical Zoology classes is formed through the integration of motivational, cognitive, practical-activity, and reflective components. The interaction of these components ensures the effective development of professional knowledge, skills, and attitudes required for successful teaching practice.

Practical classes organized on the basis of a competency-based approach contribute to strengthening students' theoretical knowledge, enhancing their professional skills, and promoting independent research activities. Such an approach enables future biology teachers to apply scientific knowledge in real educational contexts and develop the competencies necessary for their future profession.

The findings demonstrate that problem-based learning, project-based learning, research activities, the STEAM approach, and digital technologies serve as effective tools for developing practical competencies in Zoology. These methods encourage active participation, critical thinking, creativity, and the ability to solve professional problems.

The development of students' reflective abilities is also an important pedagogical factor that enhances the effectiveness of practical training and supports continuous professional growth. Reflection enables students to evaluate their performance, identify areas for improvement, and plan their future professional development.

The methodological system designed for organizing practical classes in Zoology contributes to improving the professional preparation of future biology teachers, enhancing the quality of biology education, and strengthening the practical orientation of the educational process.

In conclusion, the integration of innovative pedagogical technologies into Zoology education creates favorable conditions for the development of students' practical competencies and professional readiness. Future research should focus on exploring the educational potential of artificial intelligence technologies, virtual laboratories, and digital learning platforms in organizing practical Zoology classes and improving biology teacher education.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

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2026. №6(4)

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"Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali 26.09.2023-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №C-5669363 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: № 136361.

Manzirimiz: Toshkent shahar, Yunusobod tumani
19-mavze, 17-uy.